

Shape evolution and collective excitations in ^{190}Hg : A study using IBM1 and IBM2 models

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Abstract

The Interacting Boson Models, IBM1 and IBM2, analyzed in their O(6) limit are used to describe the properties of the ^{190}Hg isotope. A fitting procedure is used to determine the most accurate parameters to the calculated energy levels of this nucleus. The calculated ground, gamma, and beta bands energy of each model are compared to the previously measured data. Quadrupole electromagnetic transition strengths for ^{190}Hg , obtained from both IBM1 and IBM2, are presented and associated with previously experimental results. Finally, potential energy surfaces (PES) of ^{190}Hg in the dynamical symmetry O(6) of the IBM1 as an occupation of the restriction of the deformation are determined and discussed. All calculations are satisfied with experimental data.

Keywords

IBM1, IBM2, energy level, beta B(E2), potential energy, ^{190}Hg

Introduction

Iachello and Arima (Iachello and Arima 1987) proposed a new model for collective properties of the mid-mass nuclei, the Interacting Boson Model (IBM1), or more specifically, IBM1. In IBM1, the protons and neutrons were treated as bosons which were identical. IBM2 (Arima et al. 1977; Otsuka et al. 1978) adds a further distinction of bosons based on the type of nucleon they were based on

outside the closed shells. Each boson could have either of two angular momentum states, the s - boson ($L = 0$) and the d - boson ($L = 2$). In the case of even-even nuclei, IBM1 calls for a conserved number of bosons, N. The model also reproduces three limiting symmetries, which were gamma-soft O(6), vibrational U(5) and rotational SU(3) within U(6) algebra (Long et al. 1995; Iachello 2001). Several authors have proposed the existence of intermediate transitional regions of nuclei, namely,

U(5)-O(6), U(5)-SU(3), and SU(3)-O(6) (Casten and McCutchan 2007; Cejnar et al. 2010).

It is not really understood yet, why the shape coexistence and quadruple collectivity at low energies in the neutron mid-shell nuclei around the $Z = 82$ and $N = 126$ shell closures were observed. Analytical descriptions of the nuclear structure at critically point of phase transitions have attracted considerable interest during the past decades. The ^{190}Hg nucleus has 80 protons and 110 neutrons (Arima et al. 1977). Its configuration can be expressed in terms of $\pi(h11/2)^2$ and $\nu(i13/2)^{16}$, i.e. two proton holes and sixteen neutron holes with respect to the double magic nucleus ^{208}Pb . Because every nucleon interacts with every other nucleon, complex numerical methods have to be used to do the diagonalisation of the transitional Hamiltonian in these systems. Some of these configurations permit E2 transitions from yrast excited states to ground state. The nuclear structure evolution by the even-neutron deficient isotope ^{190}Hg has not been well reported in the literature. Studies of various classes of bands and B(E2) values in even-mass mercury isotopes ($A = 190$) were presented in Refs. (Garcia-Ramos and Heyde 2018; Siciliano et al. 2020; Prassa and Karakatsanis 2021). Lifetime measurements of coexistence in neutron deficient ^{188}Hg were made by Siciliano et al. 2020. Triaxial deformation-Energy surfaces showing coexistence were determined for ^{195}Hg Prassa and Karakatsanis 2021. Garcia-Ramos and Heyde 2018 used the IBM, including configuration mixing, to explain even-even isotopes of mercury in particular, and noted the relationship between the nuclear shape and shape-coherence phenomena.

Recently, application of the IBM1 and the IBM2 models of dynamical symmetry SU(3) to the ^{158}Gd nucleus (Fahmi et al. 2023) has recently been explored. Hossain et al. 2023 investigated the O(6) limit in the $^{108-112}\text{Ru}$ nuclei on the basis of IBM1 calculations. Energy level properties of the neutron-rich Er-OS nuclei with $N = 100, 102$ and 104 which were the valence nucleons of double magic nucleus ^{208}Pb nucleus was examined by Al Jubbori et al. 2018, 2020, 2022. Furthermore, more papers have studied the nuclear structure of Hg isotopes and near region by using different techniques (Hossain et al. 2014; Ahmad et al. 2021; Jameel-Un et al. 2022, 2023).

At the moment we are doing ^{190}Hg , as this is in the region between the proton shell closure at $Z = 82$ and the neutron shell closure at $N = 126$. The goal of the present manuscript is to apply the IBM1 and IBM2 models to analyses three kind of band structures, the potential energy surface and the B(E2) transition strengths of ^{190}Hg . It is assumed that this nucleus has a gamma-soft O(6) symmetry. Our systematic approach aims at relating the phenomenological interacting boson model, both IBM1 and IBM2, to the experimental data on a three energy bands, a reduced B(E2) transition strengths and the PESs of ^{190}Hg . These comparative studies of the ^{190}Hg nucleus based on an IBM1 and IBM2 model are reported here for the first time.

Calculation technique

Interacting Boson Model-1 (IBM1)

Two or more nuclei that have the same number of protons and different numbers of neutrons are referred to as isotopes. The model space for the IBM model is restricted to a smaller space. It gives a mathematical description of unpaired by coupling them in pairs, $L = 0$ or $L = 2$. The Hamiltonian for IBM1 is given in references (Iachello and Arima 1987; Casten and Warner 1988).

$$\begin{aligned} H = & \epsilon_s (s^\dagger \cdot \tilde{s}) + \epsilon_d (d^\dagger \cdot \tilde{d}) \\ & + \sum_{L=0,2,4} \frac{\sqrt{2L+1}}{2} C_L \left[(d^\dagger \times d^\dagger)^{(L)} \times (\tilde{d} \times \tilde{d})^{(L)} \right]^{(0)} \\ & + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} v_2 \left[(d^\dagger \times d^\dagger)^{(2)} \times (\tilde{d} \times \tilde{s})^{(2)} + (d^\dagger \times s^\dagger)^{(2)} \times (\tilde{d} \times \tilde{d})^{(2)} \right]^{(0)} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} v_0 \left[(d^\dagger \times d^\dagger)^{(0)} \times (\tilde{s} \times \tilde{s})^{(0)} + (s^\dagger \times s^\dagger)^{(0)} \times (\tilde{d} \times \tilde{d})^{(0)} \right]^{(0)} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} u_0 \left[(s^\dagger \times s^\dagger)^{(0)} \times (\tilde{s} \times \tilde{s})^{(0)} \right]^{(0)} + u_2 \left[(d^\dagger \times s^\dagger)^{(2)} \times (\tilde{d} \times \tilde{s})^{(2)} \right]^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The Hamiltonian of the IBM1 model is made up of nine terms. Two of them correspond to one body contributions ($L = 0$ and $L = 2$), and the parameters ϵ_s and ϵ_d are the energies of s- and d- bosons, and the others are two body interactions for which the coefficients ($C_0, C_1, C_4, v_0, v_2, u_0, u_2$) are written. The N , the number of bosons, is a conserved quantity. In total, the Hamiltonian for the IBM1 is in Eq. 1 (Arima and Iachello 1976, 1978):

$$\widehat{H} = a_0 \hat{P} + a_1 \hat{L} \cdot \hat{L} + a_2 \hat{Q} \cdot \hat{Q} + a_3 \hat{T}_3 \cdot \hat{T}_3 + a_4 \hat{T}_4 \cdot \hat{T}_4 \quad (2)$$

Boson energy $\epsilon = \epsilon_d - \epsilon_s$, and the operators are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{n}_d &= d^\dagger \cdot \tilde{d} \\ \hat{P} &= 0.5[(\tilde{d} \cdot \tilde{d}) - (\tilde{s} \cdot \tilde{s})] \\ \hat{L} &= \sqrt{10} [d^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^{(1)} \\ \hat{Q} &= [d^\dagger \times \tilde{s} + s^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^{(2)} + \chi [d^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^{(2)} \\ \hat{T}_r &= [d^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^{(r)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The four operators are indicated by the symbols $\hat{n}_d, \hat{P}, \hat{L}, \hat{Q}$ where, \hat{n}_d (total amount of d – bosons) \hat{P} (pairing), \hat{L} (angular momentum), and \hat{Q} (quadruple) operator. The \hat{T}_r denotes hexadecapole and octupole operator for $r = 4$ and 3 . The representation χ denotes to the quadrupole creation limits 0 and $\pm\sqrt{7}/2$ (Iachello 1980). The symbol a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 and a_4 are limits for the designate the $\hat{P}, \hat{L}, \hat{Q}$, and \hat{T}_r connections between the bosons.

The IBM1 makes three sorts of active symmetry and eigenvalues are given by equation 4 (Iachello 1980).

$$\begin{aligned}
E(n_d, \nu, L) &= \varepsilon n_d + \frac{a_1}{12} n_d (n_d + 4) + \left(\frac{a_3}{7} - \frac{a_1}{10} - \frac{3a_4}{70} \right) \nu(\nu + 3) + \frac{1}{14} (a_4 - a_3) L(L + 1), \quad U(5) \\
E(\lambda, \mu, L) &= \frac{a_2}{2} (\lambda^2 + \mu^2 + \lambda\mu + 3(\lambda + \mu)) + \left(a_1 - \frac{2a_2}{8} \right) L(L + 1), \\
E(\sigma, \tau, L) &= \frac{a_0}{4} (N - \sigma)(N + \sigma + 4) + \frac{a_3}{2} \tau(\tau + 3) + \left(a_1 - \frac{a_3}{10} \right) (L(L + 1)) \quad (4)
\end{aligned}$$

The symbol ε , a_0 , and a_2 indicate to the limits for U(5), O(6), and SU(3), respectively. The Hamiltonian (Arima and Iachello 1976; Iachello and Arima 1987) is familiar for the designs that break rendering to equations 5:

$$\widehat{H} = a_0 \hat{P} \cdot \hat{P} + a_1 \hat{L} \cdot \hat{L} + a_2 \hat{Q} \cdot \hat{Q} \quad (5)$$

Interacting Boson Model-2 (IBM2)

IBM2 (Arima et al. 1977; Otsuka et al. 1978) is a variant of the interacting-boson model that considers the nucleus to consist of protons and neutrons, provides for the differentiation of the two kinds of bosons, and counts their number for which the nucleons are outside the major closed shells. Each boson has a nonzero value of the angular momentum, $L = 0$ or $L = 2$, and therefore can exist in one of two states, the s-boson ($L = 0$) or the d-boson ($L = 2$). In the case of nuclei whose protons number and neutrons number is even, these bosons that represent protons and neutrons are grouped into collective states with $L = 0$ and $L = 2$. The symbol s and d represent these values of angular momentum. Bosons of protons and neutrons are

$$\widehat{V}_{pp} = \sum_{k=1,2,4} \frac{1}{2} (2L + 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} C_L^p \left[\left(d_p^\dagger \times d_p^\dagger \right)^{(L)} \cdot \left(\tilde{d}_p \times \tilde{d}_p \right)^{(L)} \right]^{(0)} \quad (9)$$

The last term, Majorana interactions $M_{\pi\nu}$, is written as equation (10).

$$M_{\pi\nu} = \xi_2 \left(s_\nu^\dagger \times d_\pi^\dagger - d_\nu^\dagger \times s_\pi^\dagger \right)^2 \cdot \left(s_\nu \times d_\pi - d_\nu \times s_\pi \right)^2 - 2 \sum_{k=1,3} \xi_k \left(d_\nu^\dagger \times d_\pi^\dagger \right)^{(k)} \cdot \left(\tilde{d}_\nu \times \tilde{d}_\pi \right)^{(k)} \quad (10)$$

If there is investigational confirmation for mixed symmetry states formerly the Majorana parameters are diverse to fix the site of these states in the spectrum. The energy level are calculated using computer code NPBOS (Otsuka and Yoshida 1985). We diagonalizable Hamiltonian of equation (7) and agree the parameters ε , k , x_π , x_ν and C_L for the best acceptable measured data.

Consequences and argument

$R_{4/2}$ classifications for symmetry

The collective energies of even-even nuclei are consists of three groups based on the ratio $R_{4/2}$:

$$R_{4/2} = \frac{E(4_1^+)}{E(2_1^+)} \quad (11)$$

where $E(4_1^+)$ the energy level at 4_1^+ and $E(2_1^+)$ is the energy level at 2_1^+ . Even-even nuclei can be classified according

denoted by p and n, respectively; therefore, s_π and s_ν are protons and neutrons s bosons ($L = 0$), and d_π and d_ν are protons, and neutrons d bosons ($L = 2$).

In IBM2, the equation (6) gives Hamiltonian as:

$$H = H_\nu + H_\pi + V_{\pi\nu} \quad (6)$$

where H_π and H_ν are the Hamiltonians of proton and neutron boson, while $V_{\pi\nu}$ is the interaction of proton-neutron.

A basic Hamiltonian (Puddu et al. 1980):

$$H = \varepsilon (\hat{n}_{d\pi} + \hat{n}_{d\nu}) + k Q_\pi \cdot Q_\nu + V_{\pi\pi} + V_{\nu\nu} + M_{\pi\nu} \quad (7)$$

Where ε_ν , ε_π are the neutron and proton energies, respectively, assumed that ($\varepsilon_\nu = \varepsilon_\pi = \varepsilon$), and the quadrupole operator is

$$Q_\rho = \left(d^\dagger \times s + s^\dagger \times \tilde{d} \right)_\rho^2 + \chi_\rho \left(d^\dagger \times \tilde{d} \right)_\rho^2 \quad \rho = \pi, \nu \quad (8)$$

where χ_ρ is a parameter to calculate the structure of the boson quadrupole operators. The relations $V_{\pi\pi} + V_{\nu\nu}$ suggest d – bosons preserving residual n-n and p-p interactions. We can get equation (9).

$$\widehat{V}_{pp} = \sum_{k=1,2,4} \frac{1}{2} (2L + 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} C_L^p \left[\left(d_p^\dagger \times d_p^\dagger \right)^{(L)} \cdot \left(\tilde{d}_p \times \tilde{d}_p \right)^{(L)} \right]^{(0)} \quad (9)$$

to ratios $R_{4/2}$ (Klein 1980; Singh and Chen 2020; NNDC 2026). The $R_{4/2} = 2.00$ indicate a harmonic vibrator U(5), $R_{4/2} = 2.50$ indicates g-unstable O(6) symmetry and $R_{4/2} = 3.33$ indicate an axially symmetric rotor SU(3)(Iachello and Arima 1987). We recognized O(6) symmetry for ^{190}Hg nucleus since $R_{4/2}$ values of nucleus is 2.5 (Singh and Chen 2020; NNDC 2026) presented in Table 1. The ratio of $E(4_1^+)/E(2_1^+)$ values as a function of even neutron numbers of ^{190}Hg isotope is shown in Fig. 1. The solid line shows U(5), O(6) and SU(3) symmetry (Iachello and Arima 1987). The solid line O(6) is near to the data ratios of $R_{4/2}$ values of ^{190}Hg isotope (Iachello and Arima 1987; Klein 1980; Singh and Chen 2020; NNDC 2026).

Table 1. The ratio $R_{4/2} = E_4 / E_2$ for even-even ^{190}Hg nucleus

Nucleus	^{190}Hg
EXP.	2.50
IBM1	2.45
IBM2	2.456

Figure 1. $E(4)/E(2)$ Vs even number of neutron of ^{190}Hg isotope. Solid line represented by error indicate U(5), O(6) and SU(3) limit.

Boson number

A boson, e.g., $s(L=0)$ or $d(L=2)$ boson, describes a pair of valence nucleons, i.e., a proton and a neutron. The boson number is determined by counting the number of pairs, of course the valence nucleons together. Valence nucleons are worked out with the help of double - mirror nuclei. In the present study, valence nucleons are counted with respect to the doubly magic nucleus ^{208}Pb ($Z=82$, $N=126$). The number of valence protons N_p and valence neutrons N_n would give a total boson number $N=N_p+N_n/2$ bosons. For this purpose, ^{208}Pb is considered an inert core for the boson counting. For ^{190}Hg nucleus, the number of valence protons and neutrons are 2 and 16, respectively. Thus the total boson number for ^{190}Hg is $(2/2+16/2)=9$ as in Table 2.

Energy levels in ^{190}Hg

We have analyzed the excitation spectra of the ground-band, gamma-band and beta band of the ^{190}Hg isotope. In both of IBM models within O(6) limit energy levels of the g-, gamma and beta band was calculated. The energy ratio $R=E_{4_1^+}/E_{2_1^+}$ is taken as an indicator of nuclear symmetry. For ^{190}Hg , a level ratio $R=2.50$ (Singh and Chen 2020; NNDC 2026) is measured which points to a deformed, gamma soft O(6) symmetry (Iachello and Arima 1987).

Table 2. The parameters used for IBM1 calculations for ^{190}Hg isotope. These parameters unit are in MeV, Furthermore, N and CHQ (χ) without unit

Nucleus	$N_\pi + N_n = N$	ϵ	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	CHQ (χ)
^{190}Hg	$1+8=9$	0.000	0.1279	0.0179	0.000	0.2203	0.000	0.000

Table 3. The parameters used for IBM2 calculations for ^{190}Hg isotope. These parameters unit are in MeV

Nucleus	$N_\pi + N_n = N$	ϵ_d	$k_{\pi\nu}$	c_π	c_n	x_2	$C_0 L_\pi$	$C_0 L_\nu(\chi)$
^{190}Hg	$1+8=9$	0.660	-0.095	-1.120	-1.300	-0.001	-0.600	-0.100
							0.000	0.100
							0.007	0.00

Tables 2, 3 shows parameters used in the calculation of IBM1 and IBM2 for the ^{190}Hg isotope, respectively. In Table 2, all the parameters are expressed in MeV and consist of the expected N and $CHQ(x)$ for the case of IBM1. In Table 3, the parameters are also given in MeV for IBM2. Table 4 contains comparative study of ground state band, gamma-band and beta-band of ^{190}Hg nucleus. The calculated data from IBM1 and 2 are in good agreement with earlier experimental measurements. Fig. 2 presents a systematic comparison of the three types of bands, which were calculated with IBM1, IBM2 and with the formerly measured data for the ^{190}Hg nucleus. The results of the calculations of the g - band in the ^{190}Hg nucleus with IBM1 and IBM2 are in satisfy to the measured data. The precision of the

Figure 2. Comparison of g-band, g-band and b-band of ^{190}Hg nucleus by IBM1, IBM2 and previous measured data (Klein 1980; Singh and Chen 2020; NNDC 2026).

calculations in the IBM2 band is higher than the precision of the calculations in the IBM1 band.

Electric Reduced Transition Probabilities B(E2)

The energy levels of excited states of even-even nuclei are given as $L_i^+ = 2_1^+, 4_1^+, 6_1^+, 8_1^+, \dots$ generally decay to the lower-lying state $L_f^+ = L_i^+ - 2$ through E2 transition. Study of strength of the reduced transition probability B(E2) is one of very important parameter to under the decay properties of a nucleus. At present work the B(E2) data were calculat-

Table 4. Comparative study of g-band, g-band and b-band in ^{190}Hg isotope by IBM1 and IBM2

J^π	g-band			J^π	g-band			J^π	b-band		
	IBM1	IBM2	EXP		IBM1	IBM2	EXP		IBM1	IBM2	EXP
0_1^+	0.000	0.000	0.000	2_2^+	1.076	1.016	1.099	0_2^+	1.280	0.923	1.278
2_1^+	0.416	0.416	0.416	3_1^+	1.932	1.481	1.657	2_3^+	1.696	1.461	1.558
4_1^+	1.020	1.022	1.041	4_2^+	1.900	1.719	1.850*	4_3^+	2.300	2.280	2.342*
6_1^+	1.812	1.624	1.772	5_1^+	2.960	2.158	–				
8_1^+	2.792	2.334	2.573*	6_2^+	2.912	2.365	2.509				

ed using the computer code PHINT (Scholten 1991), which requires values for effective charge (e_B) from Eq. (12).

$$B(E2: 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+) = \frac{\alpha_2^2}{5} N(N+4) = \frac{e_B^2}{5} N(N+4) \quad (12)$$

In order to obtain reduced transition probability values, we have close-fitting the calculated absolute strengths $B(E2)$ of transitions within ground state band to experimental ones. Value of effective charge (a_2) of IBM1 has been determined by normalizing experimental data $B(E2; 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+)$ of isotope using Eq. (12). The value of parameter a_2^2 for isotope has been calculated from the given measured value of transitions ($2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$) and used to calculate $B(E2)$ values for transitions $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$, $6_1^+ \rightarrow 4_1^+$ and $8_1^+ \rightarrow 6_1^+$. The model wave functions were found by diagonalization of the IBM2 Hamiltonian and the program NPBEM (Otsuka and Yoshida 1985) were used to estimate the electromagnetic transition.

The E2 transition operator (Lange et al. 1982):

$$T^{(E2)} = e_\pi Q_\pi + e_\nu Q_\nu \quad (13)$$

Where, Q_p is the quadrupole operator and has the same definition as in Hamiltonian (7). e_π and e_ν are boson effective charges contingent on the boson number N and they can be obtained by fitting $B(E2; 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+)$ to the measured data. The effective charge a in e_b and e_b in e_b and

$$E(N, \beta, \gamma) = \frac{N\epsilon_d\beta^2}{(1+\beta^2)} + \frac{N(N+1)}{(1+\beta^2)^2} [\alpha_1\beta^4 + \alpha_2\beta^3 \cos 3\gamma + \alpha_3\beta^2 + \alpha_4] \quad (16)$$

Alpha's parameters are the coefficients CL , v_2 , v_0 and u_0 in Eq. (1). The factor (attribute) of beta is related to the total deformation of the nucleus. A nucleus can be sphere shaped or distorted depending on whether the value of beta is equal to zero or not. Additionally, the term gamma describes the symmetry of the nucleus,

Table 5. Reduced transition probability $B(E2)_{\downarrow}$ in even-even ^{190}Hg nucleus, ($e_\pi = 0.167$, $e_\nu = 0.184$) in the IBM2

Nucleus	a e.b	Transition level	B(E2) exp. $e^2.b^2$	B(E2) IBM1 $e^2.b^2$	B(E2) IBM2 $e^2.b^2$
^{190}Hg	0.1117	$2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$	0.2921	0.2920	0.2650
		$2_2^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$	–	0.0409	0.0139
		$4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$	0.2596	0.3990	0.4351
		$4_2^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$	–	0.0320	0.0130
		$4_2^+ \rightarrow 2_2^+$	–	0.2287	0.1580
		$6_1^+ \rightarrow 4_1^+$	0.0419	0.4367	0.4201
		$8_1^+ \rightarrow 6_1^+$	–	0.4356	0.5146

$B(E2)$ value in e^2b^2 by IBM1, IBM2 and previous experimental data is presented in Table 5. The $B(E2)$ data of IBM1 and IBM2 are consistent with the measured data. The reduced transition probability $B(E2)$ is a microscopic interpretation of nuclear structure.

Potential Energy Surface (PES)

The potential energy surface (PES) gives good indication to the infinitesimal and symmetric shapes of nuclei. IBM Hamiltonian in the Refs (Bentley and Frauendorf 2011; Nomura et al. 2011; Kassim et al. 2020; Waheed et al. 2020) is used to create the PES plots using the Skyrme mean-field method. For IBM1, the energy surface is given as the expectation value of the IBM1 Hamiltonian (eq. 1) in the coherent state $|N, \beta, \gamma\rangle$ (Siciliano et al. 2020). The creation operators b_c^\dagger act on the boson vacuum $|0\rangle$ in order to create this coherent state as follows:

$$|N, \beta, \gamma\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N!}} (b_c^\dagger)^N |0\rangle \quad (14)$$

where

$$b_c^\dagger = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+\beta^2}} \left\{ s^\dagger + \beta \left[\cos\gamma (d_0^\dagger) + \sqrt{1/2} \sin\gamma (d_2^\dagger + d_{-2}^\dagger) \right] \right\} \quad (15)$$

then, the PES can be written in terms of β and γ as:

i.e., when gamma = 0, the nucleus is prolate and when gamma = 60 deg, the nucleus is oblate. Fig. 3 shows the PES contour plot for ^{190}Hg . The PES values in MeV are indicated on the color panel.

Figure 3. The PES contour plot for ^{190}Hg nucleus.

Conclusions

In the IBM1 and the IBM2 models, we examined the three types of bands ground, Gamma, and beta, the reduced transition strength B(E2) as well as the potential energy surface of ^{190}Hg . The calculated data from IBM1 and 2 are in good agreement with earlier experimental measurements. The values of the B(E2) predicted by both of these IBM calculations, IBM1 and IBM2, are consistent with the existing measurements. Potential

energy surface of ^{190}Hg is studied with IBM1. All calculations for ^{190}Hg with IBM1 and IBM2 are limited within the O(6) limit.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
